

Coumarin-3-acetic Acids.

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The investigation of coumarin-4-acetic acids and their properties (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606) has shown that these bodies resemble malonic acid in decomposing smoothly into carbon dioxide and the corresponding 4-methylcoumarins when heated to their melting point temperatures, thus:

A further point of analogy between these acids and malonic acid lies in the reactivity of the methylene group (*cf.* Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 107; 1925, 2, 227; and Dey and Seshadri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 247), the acids and their esters being found to condense readily with various aromatic aldehydes, both by Parkin's and Knoevenagel's methods, and to give rise to 4-coumarylphenyl ethylene, and 4:3-dicoumaryl derivatives. Attention was drawn in the course of these investigations to the most remarkable colour changes which occurred when alkalis acted in the cold on two of these products of condensation, *viz.*, those of 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid with (a) *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, and (b) vanillin (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 280), and the view was expressed that the most plausible explanation for these phenomena probably lay in the facility with which the molecules of those compounds which had a *para*-OH group in the benzene ring

were able to tautomerise into a form that was quinonoid both in the pyrone and in the second benzene nuclei; thus :

An inspection of the scheme given above would show that the quinonoid transformation should depend on the position of the acetic acid group, and that a coumarin having this group attached to position 3 of the pyrone ring, for example, would be expected to give products which would behave normally with alkalis. It appeared possible, therefore, that an investigation of the condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes with coumarin-3-acetic acids would provide a suitable means of testing the validity of our assumption. Although the results which have so far been obtained in this direction do not permit a definite pronouncement being made on this point, much experimental data of a new and interesting type have in the meantime been collected, the publication of which it would be unwise to delay any longer.

Coumarin-3-acetic acids do not appear to have been described in literature. The reaction between salicylaldehyde and sodium succinate, which is normally expected to furnish this acid, has been studied by Dyson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 63) who obtained only 3:3'-dicoumarin as the sole product of the reaction. A closer examination of this reaction has now been made and it is found that if only 1 molecule of the salicylaldehyde (and not an excess) is employed, and the experiment carried out under the same conditions as those described by Dyson (*loc. cit.*) a small amount of coumarin-3-acetic acid is also formed, and can be isolated together with the 3:3'-dicoumarin which still constitutes the main product of the reaction. The following equations explain the reactions that take place.

If, however, the acetic anhydride in the reaction given above be replaced by freshly made succinic anhydride, more of the coumarin acetic acid and less of the dicoumarin is formed. In a typical experiment, 6 g of salicylaldehyde yielded as much as 2.4 g. of the nearly pure coumarin-3-acetic acid, m. p. 154-55°, 2 g. of the pure

3:3'-dicoumarin (m.p. 315°), and 1.4 g. of a third product (m.p. 270°) soluble in cold alkali, which, from its chemical behaviour as well as analyses and molecular weight determinations, appears to have the structure given below.

Its formation would be readily understood if we assume that during the condensation of coumarin-3-acetic acid with salicylaldehyde, a portion of the molecules simultaneously lose carbon dioxide thus preventing the closure of the second coumarin ring, thus:

A search for other methods of obtaining coumarin-3-acetic acids has led to the discovery that members of this class may also be prepared by the condensation of phenols with either (a) ethyl formyl succinate or (b) ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of sulphuric acid. The reactions proceed in the normal manner of Pechmann's syntheses as follows: *

The reaction succeeds best with phenols having a substituent group in the *meta* position, resorcinol and α - and β -naphthols being found to give the most satisfactory results.

* A short note on this reaction was communicated to the 18th session of the Indian Science Congress held in Nagpur in January, 1931.

A noteworthy feature of the free acids is their remarkable stability, both the unsubstituted and the 4-methyl derivatives distilling unchanged at high temperatures. They present, therefore, a striking contrast with the coumarin-4-acetic acids which invariably decompose into carbon dioxide under these conditions. Although it has been possible to include in this paper only one example of the condensation of aldehydes with coumarin-3-acetic acids the methylene group in the latter has been found to be very reactive and promises to give results of considerable theoretical interest. Work in this field is now in progress and the results will be communicated shortly.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumarin-3-acetic acid.—Salicylaldehyde (6 g.), sodium succinate dried at 130° for several hours (11 g.) and freshly prepared succinic anhydride (14 g.) are heated in a flask fitted with an air-condenser at 170-80° for 4 hours. On cooling the yellow crystalline mass is transferred to a mortar with the aid of small amounts of hot water and triturated well with a cold solution of sodium bicarbonate (30 g. in 60 c. c. water). The major portion of the solid dissolves with evolution of CO₂, and after standing for an hour, the solution is filtered from the insoluble residue. The latter (4 g.) has deep yellow colour and melts indefinitely between 240° and 260°.

The clear filtrate is acidified with dilute HCl and allowed to stand overnight when clusters of beautiful pale yellow plates (2.4 g.) are deposited, m.p. 154-55°. A single crystallisation from boiling absolute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal gives shining colourless plates, m.p. 150°, yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 64.51; H, 4.06. C₁₁H₈O₄ requires C, 64.71; H, 3.92 per cent.).

The acid is extremely stable and shows no sign of decomposition even at 300°. On heating more strongly, it distils unchanged as a clear colourless liquid which rapidly solidifies (m.p. 158°). The equivalent weight was determined by titration with decinormal baryta. (Found: Eq. wt., 207.9. C₁₀H₇O₂COOH requires Eq. wt., 204.1).

Methylcoumarin-3-acetate is prepared by suspending the acid (2g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (30 c.c.) and saturating with hydrogen chloride until a clear solution is obtained, and then leaving for 12 hours. Colourless plates crystallise from hot alcohol, m.p. 77°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.3. C₁₂H₁₀O₄ requires C, 66.05; H, 4.6 per cent.).

Coumarin-3-acetanilide is best prepared by boiling the free acid (1 g.) with aniline (5 c.c.) for 2 hours, washing the product with cold dilute HCl, and then with sodium carbonate, and finally crystallising from boiling alcohol. The curious observation is made that the methyl ester of the acid does not give any anilide even on prolonged boiling with aniline. The anilide forms clusters of long colourless prisms, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent.).

The yellow residue (m.p. 240-60°) is well ground for an hour with cold *N*-caustic soda (80 c.c.) filtered and washed. The crystalline residue, after washing with alcohol, melts sharply at 315°, yield 2g. It is practically insoluble in alcohol and the other organic solvents, dissolves only in boiling alkalis and is reprecipitated unchanged on acidification, and is found to be identical in all respects with Dyson's 3:3'-dicoumarin. (Found: C, 73.9 ; H, 3.7. $C_{18}H_{10}O$ requires C, 74.5 ; H, 3.45 per cent.).

On carefully acidifying the deep orange coloured filtrate from the above, a dark sticky mass separates out ; on washing with water and standing for 24 hours, it changes into a yellow crystalline solid melting rather indefinitely (170-88°). It is purified by washing thoroughly with sodium bicarbonate solution, dissolving in cold 2 *N*-caustic soda, reprecipitating with dilute HCl, and finally crystallising twice from boiling methyl alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. Small yellow cubical crystals, m.p. 207°, yield 1.4 g. It dissolves readily in cold dilute alkalis, and decolourises bromine water and potassium permanganate solution in the cold. (Found: C, 77.1 ; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 77.27, H, 4.53 per cent.) M. W. (by elevation of boiling point of acetone), 274 ; $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires M. W., 264.

3-Coumaryl-2'-acetoxyphenyl ethylene, prepared in the usual way by heating with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine, crystallises from alcohol in groups of short colourless, needles, m.p. 177°. It is insoluble in cold alkalis but is readily deacylated on warming with alkalis and reforms the hydroxy body (m.p. 207°).

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-ethyl acetate.—Ethyl acetosuccinate (8 g. ; b.p. 150°/15 mm.) and resorcinol (4 g.) are mixed into a thin cream and slowly added to concentrated sulphuric acid (12 c.c.) cooled in ice, the flask being shaken vigorously after each addition. The clear liquid is kept in the ice-chamber overnight and then poured in a thin stream into 100 c.c. iced water. The precipitated solid is filtered after 2 hours, washed well with water and then with 30 c.c. alcohol, dried and crystallised from boiling alcohol. Colourless needles, are obtained m.p. 163°, yield 6 g. Its solution in dilute alkali exhibits a bright blue fluorescence characteristic of umbelliferons. (Found: C, 64·36; H, 5·43. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64·09; H, 5·38 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid.—The ethyl ester (m.p. 163°) is dissolved in 2*N*-caustic soda, and the solution warmed to 50-60° on the water-bath for 15 minutes. On cooling and acidifying the solution, the coumarin-3-acetic acid comes down slowly in the form of fine needles. It is crystallised once from hot 50 p.c. alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 265°. (Found: C, 61·06; H, 4·76. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61·57; H, 4·41 per cent.).

The *silver salt* is thrown down as a curdy white precipitate. (Found: Ag, 31·04. $C_{12}H_9O_5$ Ag requires Ag, 31·6 per cent.).

The calcium and the barium salts are sparingly soluble in water, and crystallise well from the hot solutions on cooling. [Found: Ca, 5·05. $(C_{12}H_9O_5)_2$ Ca, 11 H_2O , requires Ca, 5·68 per cent. Ba, 15·40. $(C_{12}H_9O_5)_2$ Ba, 16 H_2O requires Ba, 15·37 per cent.].

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-ethyl acetate, prepared by shaking a cold alkaline solution of 7-hydroxycoumarin-3-ethyl acetate with methyl sulphate and acidifying the mixture; crystallises in colourless needles melting at 80°.

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid, obtained from the above by the action of warm 2*N*-caustic soda, crystallises from 30 p.c. alcohol in colourless plates melting at 198°. (Found: Eq. wt., 231. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 248). The acid is very stable and distils unchanged at a high temperature.

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-methyl acetate, from the acid, methyl alcohol and hydrogen chloride, crystallises in colourless needles, m.p. 122°.

7-Acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-ethyl acetate, forms colourless plates, m.p. 98°.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetamide.—On warming the ethyl ester with alcoholic ammonia, a yellow solution is obtained from which the free acid (m.p. 265°) can be recovered. The amide is best prepared by the method described by Buck and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1679). The dry acid is melted in a small flask heated to 270° in a castor oil-bath and dry ammonia gas is passed over the molten acid for 2 hours. The solid is then ground with sodium bicarbonate solution, left for half an hour, filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. 0.8 G of colourless needles, m.p. 300° (decomp.) are obtained from 2 g. of the acid. (Found: N, 5.81. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.45 per cent.). The amide is hydrolysed on boiling for some time with 10 p. c. caustic soda, regenerating the acid (m.p. 267°).

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetanilide.—This is obtained by boiling the acid (but not the ethyl ester) with aniline for 2 hours, pouring the liquid into dilute hydrochloric acid, washing the precipitated yellow solid with sodium bicarbonate solution, and crystallising it from alcohol in long colourless feathery needles, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 4.66. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.53 per cent.).

7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-3-coumaryl-3'-coumarin.—The dry sodium salt of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid (2.6 g.), salicylaldehyde (4 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) are heated to 160-70° under reflux for 8 hours. The warm liquid is poured into 100 c.c. of ice water with vigorous stirring and the precipitated red oil washed twice by decantation. It is left in contact with a little absolute alcohol when the oil changed in the course of 24 hours into brittle mass. This is filtered, washed repeatedly with small amounts of cold alcohol in which it dissolves very sparingly, and then crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid with the addition of animal charcoal in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 268°, insoluble in cold alkalis and sparingly soluble in most organic solvents. (Found: C, 69.01; H, 3.97. $C_{21}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 69.6; H, 3.9 per cent.).

4-Methyl- α -naphthopyrone-3-ethyl Acetate.

α -Naphthol (4 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (7 g.) are condensed in presence of cold concentrated sulphuric acid, and the product worked up in the usual manner. The ester crystallises from methyl alcohol in long colourless needles, m.p. 139° , yield 2 g. (Found: C, 72.95; H, 5.56. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.97; H, 5.45 per cent.).

4-Methyl- α -naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid.—The ethyl ester (1 g.) is boiled with 2*N* caustic soda (20 c.c.) until the solid dissolves completely (about half an hour). The cold solution is filtered and acidified when a white precipitate is immediately formed. It is purified by dissolving in sodium bicarbonate, reprecipitating with acid, and crystallising the dry precipitate from hot glacial acetic acid in colourless shining plates, m.p. 251° . (Found: Eq. wt., 273. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires Eq. wt., 268).

The *silver salt* is precipitated as a pale yellow microcrystalline powder. (Found: Ag, 28.8. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4$ Ag requires Ag, 28.8 per cent.).

The *calcium* and the *barium salts* are thrown down as crystalline precipitates on adding calcium and barium chloride to a neutral solution of the acid.

4-Methyl- α -naphthapyrone-3-acetanilide.—The curious observation made in the case of the 7-hydroxycoumarin derivative is repeated here; the ethyl ester does not react with aniline even on prolonged boiling. The anilide is made from the free acid by the method described before. Boiling with 20 p.c. caustic soda for 15 minutes reconverts it into the acid, m.p. 251° . (Found: N, 4.3. $C_{22}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5.08 per cent.).

4-Methyl- β -naphthapyrone-3-acetic Acid.

This acid and not the expected ethyl ester, is formed on condensing β -naphthol and ethyl acetosuccinate in the usual manner. The product crystallises from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 199° . (Found: Eq. wt., 272.9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires Eq. wt., 268).

ββ-Methyl-2-hydroxynaphthylitaconic Acid.

β-Naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid (m.p. 199°, 2 g.) is dissolved in 26 c.c. of 2*N*-caustic soda and the solution boiled for half an hour. On cooling and acidifying the solution it becomes turbid and then soft colourless plates, refracting light like jewels, slowly separate out. After an hour the crystals are filtered, washed with cold water, and dried on porous plate. They melt sharply at 154° giving off steam and then solidify again. The residue which melts at 198° is identified with 4-methyl-*β*-naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid by a mixed melting point. Boiling with alcohol or acetic acid is also found to result in ring closure, the acid (m.p. 198°) crystallising after some time. A 50 p. c. methyl alcoholic solution of the itaconic acid was exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hours but no change was observed, the acid (m.p. 154°) being thrown down on addition of water. It is curious to note, however, that on leaving the alcoholic solution in the dark overnight, the *β*-naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid (m.p. 198°) crystallises out, showing that ring closure had been effected even in the cold in the dark. (Found: Eq. wt., 142.5. C₁₆H₁₄O₅ requires Eq. wt., 143).

4-Methyl-*β*-naphthapyrone-3-ethyl acetate, prepared by esterifying the acid, forms hard colourless prisms, m.p. 101°. The ester, on hydrolysis with hot or even cold alkali, gives the itaconic acid (m.p. 150°), which, on heating, changes into the stable acetic acid (m.p. 198°). (Found: C, 73.6; H, 5.3. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 73.0; H, 5.4 per cent.).

4-Methyl-*β*-naphthapyrone-3-methyl acetate crystallises in short colourless prisms, m.p. 137°.

β-Naphthapyrone-3-acetic Acid.

β-naphthol (5.6 g.) and ethyl formylsuccinate (8 g.) are mixed and added to cold sulphuric acid in the usual way. On pouring the liquid after 24 hours into excess of water, a red oil separates which is washed several times by decantation with cold decinormal alkali. It changes into a yellow semi-solid mass but does not completely solidify. It is therefore hydrolysed by boiling with 2*N*-caustic soda until a clear solution is obtained, filtered and acidified, when a sticky resinous mass is precipitated which becomes granular on standing in contact with water for 24 hours. It is purified by dissolving in cold sodium bicarbonate solution, filtering from a small amount of insoluble matter, precipitating with hydrochloric acid and finally crystallising twice from boiling methyl alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 265°. (Found: Eq. wt., 258. C₁₅H₁₀O₄ requires Eq. wt., 254).

β-naphthapyrone-3-methyl acetate, prepared from the acid by esterification with methyl alcohol and hydrogen chloride, crystallises from methyl alcohol in long prismatic needles, m.p. 149°. (Found: C, 70.51 ; H, 4.22. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.47 per cent.).

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